

**Model curricula for Mongolian journalism education: its vision and reforms
in the new, democratic period**

Abstract

Mongolia has a population of only 3 million, who attain information and entertainment from 555 media organisations in the media market. The journalists who work for those media organisations have been trained by 19 universities and institutions. Journalism education has a 64 year history in the country's 100 year history of journalism. State and private journalism training institutions delivering academic journalism education have largely followed the traditional forms of the Soviet Union. Despite attempts at implementing American and Western style curriculum design for journalism education in Mongolia, many have claimed that this has not been implemented adequately so far. There is a demand for redesigning the journalism curricula to incorporate technological developments and changes in the society in addition to public attitudes towards the media. The article is aiming at analyse the curricula of the journalism training institutions of Mongolia in order to clarify whether they meet the needs of students, employers and labor market.

INTRODUCTION

After declaring independence in 1921 with the People's Revolution, Mongolia became a socialist satellite state that followed the model of the Soviet Union in terms of political and economic orientation. At that time, the Mongolian media played an important role in promoting the ideology of the one ruling party. In 1990, Mongolia became a democratic country as a result of movements for democracy in the Soviet Union and southern Europe in 1989-1990. Since then, state control of the activities and content of the media collapsed, and the number of media organizations increased to 1 television channel, 37 newspapers and 32 journals in the late 1980s (Lombo, 2003, p. 216). Furthermore, there was a rapid increase in the number of media organisations, which grew to 663 in a short period of time (Maulet, 1997, p. 15). Moreover, the process of obtaining higher education expanded as a result of private sector involvement regulated by laws and there was a high demand for educated human resources in the labor market. State universities transferred to the self-funding system whereby students pay their tuition fees and the number of private universities increased as well.

A recent study (The World Bank, 2010, p. 2) highlighted that in 1991 there were 14 state universities with 20,000 students, but by 2009 this number reached 151 (42 of these were state universities) with a total number of 150,326 students. Until the 1960s, journalists who were working in the Mongolian journalism sector, established in 1913, were not professionals; instead they were naturally talented, self-taught individuals or those who only completed short-term courses. In other words, Mongolian journalism initially developed based on our cultural heritage, traditional script and "Mongol intelligence". From the middle of the 1950s, Mongolian journalists were educated in Moscow and Leningrad, Bulgaria and East Germany. Thus, from the middle of

1950s and 1960s, newly graduated and highly educated journalists returned to work in their home country, which became the impetus for implementing scientific methods in Mongolian journalism practice. Those returning journalists also contributed greatly to preparing future journalists locally (Lombo, 2001, p. 210).

The National University of Mongolia (NUM) commenced its journalism courses in the 1960-1961 academic year and one year later the department of journalism was set up and invited I.I. Demiyanchuk, who was an associate professor in the Kiev University journalism department, in order to enrich the journalism curriculum and improve the teaching methodology and professional knowledge of the local teachers. Later, the journalism department moved to the Institute of Marxism-Leninism which was under the central committee of the Mongolian People's Revolutionary Party (MPRP) and 6 cohorts graduated between 1967 and 1977. In addition to this, the Marxism and Leninism evening course of the central committee of the MPRP in Ulaanbaatar prepared about 370 journalists. Once Mongolia transferred to the new system, more opportunities to study abroad opened, and a few people began studying at postgraduate level in the United Kingdom, Germany and the United States of America and a number of students studied in Russia at the undergraduate level. Compared to the 1990s, when only one university offered a journalism course, in 2006, 22 state and private universities were teaching journalism at the undergraduate level. Some state and private universities also offered postgraduate journalism education beginning in 1996. According to the report prepared by the Press Institute (2013, p. 66), 555 media organizations were operating in Mongolia in 2012, with 4903 full-time employees, 2341 of whom were creative employees such as journalists, reporters, editors and producers. In terms of academic majors, 867 of them were professional journalists. However, a total of 4609 journalists were prepared from 1965 to 2012 and it is clear that 400 professional journalists are annually sent to the

media sector. Approximately 20% of them specialised as international journalists, journalists- interpreters, journalists-literary authors, radio and television journalists, television journalists- cameramen, television journalists-producers, and sports journalists through single or dual major programs.

The information showed that 440 journalism students completed the bachelor's program last year, 33 students went through the master's degree program and 2 students earned a Ph.D. in journalism. As of 2014, in all, 1749 students were studying for bachelor's degrees in journalism at the 5 state universities and 12 private universities, 1315 of whom were women. 78 students were in master's degree courses and 26 were studying for a Ph.D. Nowadays, 19 universities are offering journalism courses and 428 students were expected to finish their courses by 2014.

TABLE 1
Mongolian journalism training institutions /March, 2014/

№	Journalism training institutions	Current students	Graduates for 2014
1	National University of Mongolia, Department of Journalism	215	48
2	National University of Mongolia, Ulaanbaatar University	44	44
3	University of the Humanities	116	33
4	University of the Humanities, Darkhan University	30	-
5	Mongolian State University of Education	87	11
6	Mongolian State University of Education, School of Mongolian Language and Culture	143	27
7	Mongolian State University of Culture and Arts, School of Radio and Television	323	71
8	Otgontenger University	105	20
9	Ider Institute	55	10
10	Zohiomj Institute	188	61
11	Ulaanbaatar-Erdem University	48	15
12	Ih Zasag University	61	-
13	Journalist College	82	21
14	Orkhon University	17	8
15	Institute of International Studies	24	7

16	Soyol-Erdem Institute	40	7
17	Institute of Literature and Social Workers	30	7
18	Mongolian University of Culture and Arts, School of Film and Art	82	23
19	Ih Mongol Institute	59	15
Total		1749	428

There is a demand for preparing qualified journalists in the labor market of Mongolia. This is unlikely to change in the coming years. The number of media organizations is expected to increase because of the current situations where the laws are not implemented properly and media are influenced by power. This hypothesis, which was made two years ago, has been proven (Author citation, 2011, p. 158). This crisis in the whole system of journalism might change when politicians and businessmen no longer use the media to protect themselves.

Currently, there are a number of newly established television stations and internet sites being set up. It is expected that the number of internet sites will increase in the future. Newly graduated journalists are criticized in terms of their professional qualifications and ethics by both mass media users and media owners. Therefore, it is important to clarify and analyse the reasons in order to improve the situation in the future. Particularly, the curriculum of higher education becomes a basis for preparing journalists who are able to analyse and synthesize issues, consider their professional duties, gain the required qualifications for the journalistic style of writing and follow the principles and teachings of free media. Therefore, research on the journalism curriculum at Mongolian universities has been conducted.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This article focuses on several projects and research which have been initiated by the state and universities in order to redesign and improve journalism curricula since 1990. Until 1990, the

content of journalism curricula was based on the experiences of Soviet universities and reflected their national features. However, new principles and strategies started being implemented in the practice and theory of journalism in the 1990s when Mongolia introduced a new policy for their foreign relations. However, there were still several issues at many journalism training institutions regarding the curriculum, insufficient training resources and materials, lack of both professional teachers and subjects. Therefore, the research project “The current situation and future perspectives of journalism training in Mongolia” was conducted by the Open Society Institute /Soros Foundation/ and NUM Journalism Department in 1998.

As a result of this, the importance of redesigning the content of journalism training was investigated. Based on the findings of this project, another 3-year research project “Improving the journalism curriculum at Mongolian universities” was implemented by the NUM Journalism Department and Missouri University in the USA in 1999. As a result of this research project, the main documentation including the curriculum at the NUM was redesigned, made it closer to the global standards and offered to all institutions preparing journalists. Afterwards, the Mongolian National Council of Standards and Measurement approved the bachelor’s degree program standard for ‘Journalism’ in 2003. The Law of Education (2006) requires all higher education institutions to adhere to the higher education standards that are set down in this Law. It is the document which determines the main principles in the content of higher education, its evaluation, and the professional level of teachers and institutions. The journalism training standard is based on the sample rule of the Mongolian Ministry of Education, Culture and Sciences (MECS), and some aspects of the education standards of developed countries (USA, Russia, Germany) are considered in it (Maulet, 2013). As a result of this standard, the percentage of new trends and practical subjects was increased in the curriculum and for the first time the standard combining both theory and

practice was approved. Therefore, journalism students complete about 60 different courses in which they earn 124-128 credit hours for their 4-year bachelor's degree course. Professional subjects account for 55% of the curriculum and practical subjects, 44%. The MECS of Mongolia demands that journalism training institutions follow this standard so the curricula and their content at different institutions are similar. However, those institutions may enrich the curricula in terms of their features. Therefore, the universities redesign the content of the curriculum every 2-3 years and they are approved by the Department of Professional Education of the MECS. This is one of the biggest improvements which were made in journalism training since 1990. Due to the research project and standards, the quality of journalism training has been improving (Author citation, 2013). However, the implementation process of this research project was completed in 2009 and the pace of improving the standards is slow at the moment. Therefore, this standard cannot meet the modern needs of the journalism training.

In 2010, the Journalism College of the Press Institute decided to translate "Model curricula for journalism education in developing and democratic countries", which is one of the journalism education series by UNESCO (2006), and deliver it to the universities in order to prepare to design a model curriculum for Mongolian journalism education. Within the scope of this initiative, 7 curricula for basic journalism and practical journalism were improved and one new curriculum for development journalism was designed. This was done through the cooperation of ten state and private universities and their professors, who worked on this in groups in order to compare the curricula. As a result, the model curriculum for Mongolian journalism has been completed. Although some universities have been using those 8 curricula, it has been criticised by the other professors' teams, who consider this curriculum model to be out of date and useful only for

developing countries. In general, these steps played a major role in Mongolian journalism, although journalists who can compete in the international labor market have not yet been prepared.

There is a lack of research on the journalism curriculum in Mongolia. Therefore, the conference on “Improving the content of Journalism curriculum” was held and funded by the Soros Foundation in order to seek possible ways to solve issues facing journalism training. However, it could not focus on the journalism curriculum, instead it discussed the changes in higher education, the methodology of teaching specific subjects and effective ways of organizing practice. In this conference, the difficulties of journalism training were explained in terms of the qualifications of professional teachers, resources, materials and qualities of students (Lhagvasuren, 2001, p. 28). Additionally, some researchers wrote an article for the NUM’s prestigious scientific journal “Journalism” on the quality of Mongolian journalism training after comparing training in Mongolia and India (Norovsuren, 2012). However, they still considered the reasons regarding the training environment, teachers and resources and could not recommend how to improve the quality of journalism training in Mongolia (Dorjgotov, 2011). Other articles published in the journal suggested some ways to improve the standards for Mongolian journalism training curriculum. These proved that researchers do not consider the curriculum as an important aspect of journalism training when they approach the issues investigating difficulties and possible ways to improve the journalism training. However, it should be pointed out that the curriculum is the key documentation which describes required knowledge and skills of graduates.

METHOD

This article analyses the journalism curricula of 19 universities in Mongolia and includes a focus group interview to collect the data from the heads of the journalism departments. The article

compared the two main surveys; “Current circumstances of Mongolian journalism training” from the journalism teachers and administration of those 19 universities in February 2013 and “Satisfaction survey among journalism students” which involved students majoring in journalism in April 2011.

SAMPLE

A journalism curriculum is designed based on the laws of Mongolian education, international trends of journalism higher education and comparison of foreign universities that offer similar programs. The curriculum in Mongolian higher education consists of 4 main components; general basics /A/, professional basics /B/, specializations/C/ and internship /D/. The structure is drawn, as follows: A:B:C:D=40-42: 50-52: 28-32: 5 credit hours. The general basics include subjects which students must study in order to obtain higher education in Mongolia such as philosophy, politics and culture studies that contain the required knowledge of democracy and development that are included by UNESCO in the evaluation criteria of academic training programs. Professional basics contain the necessary subjects which journalism students must study and include the theory of journalism, theory of public communication, journalistic style of writing and editing methodology. Specializations focus on the subjects providing specific knowledge and skills such as ecology journalism, investigative journalism, studies and criticism of journalism and advertisement of public media. In addition to those subjects, students can choose subjects related to media such as the radio, television and newspapers, depending on their future working fields.

Table 2 shows the comparative structure of the NUM journalism curriculum in order to illustrate the general structure of journalism curriculum in the democratic period. The NUM is the oldest university and has been offering journalism courses for the longest time in Mongolia.

TABLE 2

Comparison of the NUM journalism education curricula in the democratic period

Journalism curricula (1996)	Journalism curricula (2003)	Journalism curricula (2014)
	<i>Professional basics</i>	
1. Theoretical foundation of journalism	1. Theory of journalism	1. Theory of journalism
2. Communication of majority	2. Newspaper photographs	2. Practical journalism- I
3. Newspaper photographs	3. Public communication	3. Practical journalism-II
4. Theory and Practice of the press	4. Journalist's skills	4. Practical journalism-III
5. News editing	5. History of Mongolian journalism	5. Journalist's ethics
6. Newspaper design	6. News editing	6. Journalist's skills
7. Journalist's skills	7. Foundation and organization of public media	7. Foundation and organization of public media
8. History of Mongolian journalism	8. Theory of social communication	8. Photojournalism
9. Foreign journalism	9. Newspaper design	9. Stylistics of an article and broadcast
10. Sociology of journalism	10. Studies of journalism	10. News editing methodology
11. Advertising	11. Practical journalism-I	11. Information and communication design
12. Journalist's ethics	12. Practical journalism-II	12. History of Mongolian journalism- I
13. Theory and methodology of journalism	13. Practical journalism-III	13. History of Mongolian journalism -II
	14. Television journalism	14. Radio journalism-I
	15. Radio television	15. Television journalism-I
	16. Foreign journalism	16. Public relations and communication
	17. Law of public media	17. Foreign journalism
		18. Law of public media
	<i>Core specializations</i>	
B. Elective units	A.Core units	Core units
1. Newspaper journalism	1. Management of public media	19. Advertising of public media
2. Radio journalism	2. Sociology of journalism	20. Management of public media
3. Television journalism	3. Journalism of ecology	21. Journalism of ecology
4. International journalism	4. Investigative journalism	22. Investigative journalism
	5. Advertising of public media	23. Journalism study and critique

<p>B. Elective units</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Newspaper journalism 2. Radio journalism II 3. Television journalism II 4. Advertising of public media II 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 24. Marketing of public media 25. Sociology of journalism 26. Theory of public relations \PR\ 27. Electronic press <p>B. Elective units</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Newspaper journalism 2. Radio journalism-II 3. Television journalism-II 4. Advertising of public media-II
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According to the data in 1983, graduates of journalism courses studied 37 different courses for 4200 academic hours including “The history of Russian journalism”, “Press history of the party and state of the Soviet Union”, “Press history of Communist labor parties” and “Press history of the Mongolian People’s Republic”. In addition to this, 11 different courses were offered for about 1300 academic hours such as “Theory and practice in the Mongolian press”, “Technical formatting and design of newspaper”, “Photography”, “Elective courses” (Maulet & Lombo, 2010, p.17). It is seen that history subjects dominated in this period. In accordance with the tasks set by the Central Committee of the Mongolian People’s Revolutionary Party, some professional subjects were taught in Russian.

Since 1990, the redesigned curriculum has been used according to the education systems of democratic societies and there has been a huge change in teaching methods, structure of subjects and terminologies. By 1996, history subjects, in particular the theory of the Communist Party, were taken out of the curriculum. However, only 14 of all 42 subjects were professional subjects and others were general basics including the study of economics and politics in order to provide

basic knowledge of social science for journalists. In addition to this, there was a concern that journalists must be familiar with all areas of knowledge. Therefore, foundation courses in agriculture, history of arts, and the foundation of religion were introduced. There were 18 weeks for preparatory and final internships.

7 years later, the curriculum was changed dramatically as a result of the 3-year project “Improving the journalism curriculum” with professors of Missouri University and standards of journalism education. Due to this, the number of professional subjects increased, and now 23 of all 48 subjects are related to their profession. It should be emphasised that there are 3 levels of courses for practical journalism, including investigative journalism, environmental journalism, management and law of mass media. Currently, the NUM offers a 128-credit-hour journalism course in which professional, specialization and elective courses were increased up to 28 credit hours. They tried to include all issues related to journalism in this curriculum, such as public relations (PR), internet press, marketing of mass media, and stylistics of journalistic writing. There are 20-week internships in this curriculum. Lately, students are increasingly interested in public relations in addition to journalism. Therefore, the universities included public relations and advertising in their curriculum. It will help to expand students’ flexibility in the labor market and also influence several issues such as journalists’ salaries, changes in media technology and unclear market situations.

Table 3 presents the comparison of three of the 19 universities that offer journalism courses based on the results of the students’ satisfaction survey which included 246 students of 18 universities and colleges. According to the survey, these 3 universities are ranked 2nd, 3rd and 5th on the list. The NUM ranks highest.

TABLE 3

Journalism curricula of the top universities delivering journalism education in Mongolia

Enrollment in local colleges, 2005

Mongolian State University of Education	Mongolian University of Culture and Arts – Institute of Radio and Television	University of the Humanities
	<i>Professional basics</i>	
1. Theory of social communication	1. Foundation of mass media	1. Introduction of journalism theory
2. Public relations	2. Rhetoric-I	2. Theory of social information communication
3. Law regulations of public media	3. Rhetoric -II	3. Mass communication and society
4. History of foreign journalism	4. Foundation of journalism theory	4. Foundation and organization of mass media
5. History of Mongolian journalism	5. History of Mongolian journalism	5. Genre of writing
6. Fundamental journalism –I	6. News editing	6. History of Mongolian journalism
7. Fundamental journalism–II	7. Journalist’ ethics	7. History of the world journalism
8. Fundamental journalism- III	8. Sociology of journalism	8. Journalist’s skills-I
9. Fundamental journalism- IV	9. Theory of mass communication	9. Journalist’s skills-II
10. Practical journalism -1	10. Law regulation of mass media	10. Practical journalism-I
11. Practical journalism -2	11. Theory of Mongolian journalism	11. Practical journalism-II
12. Practical journalism -3	12. Research methodology	12. Practical journalism-III
13. Journalist’s skills	13. Investigative journalism	13. Radio journalism
14. Advertising of mass media	14. Management of mass media	14. Photo for newspaper
15. Press management-I	15. Modern Mongolian language	15. News editing
16. Press management –II	16. Techniques, technology of radio and television	16. Journalist’s ethics
17. Journalist’s ethics-I	17. Digital journalism	17. Law and regulation of mass media
18. Journalist’s ethics-II		18. Investigative journalism
19. Research methodology and sociology of journalism		
20. Internet journalism		
21. Press design		
	<i>Core specialization</i>	
1. Modern Mongolian language-I	1. Basics of presenter’s skills	1. Journalism critique and study
2. Modern Mongolian language-II	2. Montage	2. International journalism
3. Development journalism	3. Culture of presenter and sanitation	3. Environmental journalism
4. Stylistics-I	4. Radio production	4. Newspaper design
5. Stylistics-II	5. Foreign journalism	5. Data journalism
		6. Public relations /PR/

6. Mongolian literature -I	6. Practical journalism-radio journalist's skill-I	7. Management of mass media
7. Mongolian literature-II	7. Practical journalism-radio journalist's skill-II	8. Sociology of journalism
8. Foreign literature-I	8. Practical journalism-television journalist's skill-I	9. Citizen journalism
9. Foreign literature -II	9. Practical journalism-television journalist's skill-II	10. Journalism of politics
10. Audio and video production	10. TV production	11. Journalism of economics
11. Radio and television journalism -I	11. Public relations	12. Online journalism
12. Radio and television journalism -II	<i>Elective units</i>	
Journalist and photo journalist	1. Journalist's skills	• Foundation of advertising
• Aesthetics	2. Stylistics	• Interactive multimedia
• Foundation of investigative journalism	3. Foundation of camera processor	• Tele journalism
• Journalism of politics	4. Foundation of drama	Tele-journalist
• Culture and civilization		• Theory and practice of tele-journalism
• Photo journalism		• Professional skills of tele-journalist
• News editing methodology		• Technical activities of television
• Modern issues of journalism		Multimedia journalist
Journalist		• Digital media
• Journalism of economics and business		• Writing for web
• News editing methodology		• Development of multimedia
• Journalism studies and critique		Advertising copywriter
• Journalism of culture and arts		• Theory and practice of advertising
• Methodology of investigative journalism		• Artistic creation of advertising
• Citizen journalism		• Methodology of advertising organization
• Theoretical and practical issues of journalism		
	<i>Internship</i>	
1. Introductory internship	1. Introductory internship	1. Introductory internship
2. Workplace internship	2. Workplace internship	2. Workplace internship
3. Final internship before graduation	3. Final internship before graduation	3. Final internship before graduation
Total	998	908

This comparison shows that the structures of the curricula are fairly similar (Table 3). These curricula are also similar to the structure of the NUM curriculum. The reason is that the MECS demands that universities follow the old journalism standards and most universities use the NUM journalism curriculum as a model.

From the research findings, although the curricula are fairly similar, every university has its own features and advantages. For instance, the University of the Humanities prepares journalists with knowledge of information technology and included these types of subjects in the curriculum. The Mongolian State University of Education focuses on journalistic writing skills and preparing newspaper journalists. Therefore, there is great emphasis on modern Mongolian language, stylistics and literature in the curriculum. The Institute of Radio and Television of the University of Culture and Arts is recognized for training radio and television journalists, thus its main focus is on hosting skills, the culture of hosts, montage and skills of radio and television journalists.

The comparison of the 19 curricula reveals that 16 subjects, including the theory of journalism, skills of journalists, practical journalism, journalist's ethics, foundation of mass media, history of Mongolian journalism, history of foreign journalism, editing methodology, sociology of journalism, advertising of mass media, law of mass media, newspaper design, photo journalism, investigative journalism, radio journalism and tele-journalism are included in all curricula. However, journalism of politics, journalism of business and economics, citizen journalism are in only 12 curricula (63%). Online journalism study and critiques are in 8 curricula (42%), international journalism is in 6 curricula (32%), theory of social communication and public relations are in 5 curricula (26%). Furthermore, development journalism, data journalism, interactive multimedia, digital media, writing for web, development of multimedia, mass

information communication and society, mass information communication, marketing of mass media, journalism of culture and arts, production of audio and video, and culture of hosting are included in only one curriculum.

According to the findings from the professors' surveys, although the current standard of journalism does not meet the current needs adequately, professors use them as a model and some of UNESCO's sample curriculum is included as well. The answers given by professors are very similar. One of the survey participants, a professor at the Ulaanbaatar Erdem Oyu University said, "My university designs our curriculum based on the curriculum of the journalism department at Moscow University". The head of the Otgontenger University journalism department answered that they use the curriculum of the Uralian University, Russia as a model and Ming Chuan University, Taiwan, as well because they have a student exchange program with Ming Chuan University.

Those universities follow the Russian style curriculum because their professors who graduated from Russian universities and have used this for many years. The head of the Journalism Department of the Mongolian State University of Education completed a masters' degree in England so its curriculum follows liberal journalism standards, while the head, who graduated from the Uralian University, uses the Russian standards. Therefore, it is evident that curriculum design depends on the department head's educational background and the language they use for research and study. The universities in this comparison determine their features through practice-dominated courses. However, the research shows that they are theory-dominated courses. Generally, it is not easy to organize practice-dominated training in the current Mongolian situation

because of a lack of modern materials and techniques in which the training is held in order to bring their theory and practice closer together.

Although most universities have their own studios, computer laboratories, and other equipment for reporting, many of the facilities are not sufficient for all students and can be used properly only for a few tasks. In other words, there is limited press production at universities. According to the research, 5 universities who offer journalism courses do not have a professional studio or a single camera.

The Press Institute's Journalist College could establish its image as a practice-dominated training institution. They design the journalism curriculum based on Arhus University, Denmark, and Missouri University. However, their training does not yet meet western standards, because the training returned to the Mongolian model after the Danish professors left the country. The research which aimed at determining the current situations and problems facing Mongolian journalism involved the professors and head of the department. They think that the journalism training is criticized by both the Press Institute and the public because the the students' low level of knowledge and insufficient equipment. Only 10% of the professors think that the curriculum should be developed or redesigned.

The survey which was conducted in 2014 revealed that 67% of the universities redesigned the curriculum in 2013 and the rest of them were thinking of changing their curricula in 2014 but they didn't know what kinds of changes had to be made. In other words, these universities argued that they had always improved their curricula so they considered that the curricula that they were using met the desired standards. Although universities redevelop their curricula once every 3-4 years, it has not brought any decisive advantages yet. In most cases, basic subjects which are approved by

the MECS are changed and then the curricula has to be changed. The main changes in the curricula include several subjects such as citizen journalism, journalism of economics, journalism of politics, online journalist and development journalism.

The findings of the satisfaction survey of journalism students which was conducted in 2011 and 2013 illustrated that 65% of the students answered that they were satisfied with their journalism course. This is better than the finding in 2011 which revealed 56% satisfaction. Additionally, the students who were not satisfied with their course explained their reasons in terms of the lack of resources, inappropriate learning environment and curricula.

Figure 1

The reasons for dissatisfaction

Although the majority of students (65%) were planning to work in the television sector in 2011, the number of those students decreased by 2% in 2013. In addition to this, 16% of students want to work in the department of public relations, 13% in newspapers, 6% in radios, and 2% in internet sites.

According to the research results, the modern students wanted to study more courses such as skills of radio and television hosts (44%), computer and graphic design (21%), online journalism (14%), skills of journalists (14%) and other important subjects (7%). Judging from this research, students are mostly interested in the television sector because of the television “flood” which occurred in Mongolia in recent years. In 2014, there were 138 regular television channels and 24 cable channels in Mongolia. It seems that Mongolian students prefer the television sector while American students are keener on digital journalism (Becker et al., 2012, p. 345).

CONCLUSION

To sum up, journalism education at Mongolian state and private universities is still following the traditional Soviet-style curricula. The journalism curricula are out of date regarding societal and technological developments as well as people’s attitudes towards information. However, researchers have focused on curricula less and the state requires the universities to follow the old standards. In this case, the curricula which were designed based on the old standards that were approved 10 years later cannot be changed. Furthermore, there are several issues which influence the quality of journalism training, such as restrictions in curricula choice, and the lack of a general idea in the content and quality. The universities do not consider the needs and wishes of employers, civil society, and research organizations when they design the curricula.

Although some changes have been made at universities depending on their features, it is time to change the journalism curricula entirely. The role of journalism has been increasing in our rapidly developing society in terms of its power to influence the society’s psychology. On the other hand, journalism as a unique element of the social and political structure has to be changed. As a result,

the role, goals, statutes and new information technology should be considered at a different level.

It is necessary to change the curricula for all those reasons.

Curricula require ongoing development and improvement so that students are able to learn every single change in of the media sector and professors need to improve themselves professionally.

Two main curricula changes in Mongolian journalism training are required:

- It is necessary to increase the number of curricula which develop students' basic knowledge and professional value. As a result, a journalist who is aware of a valuable component of civil democratic principle illustrates the history of his/her country and other nationalities through pluralism, respect for others' views in a conflicted situation and is able to analyse events and issues objectively, is good at making decisions and able to take responsibility for both him/herself and others. Therefore, the curricula must emphasize critical thinking, curiosity and knowledge about the world and humanitarian journalism and intercultural journalism according to the UNESCO model curricula (2013) as well.
- Moreover, students should gain required qualifications for modern journalism and be able to make changes, taking into consideration the advantages of modern science and technology. It is expected that digital journalism will continue to develop rapidly because of the various information channels. In this case, it is impossible to use the traditional, old-fashioned curricula. Therefore, writing for the web, using the web reporting, using social media, animation for the web, digital storytelling, creating and using blogs, creating content for mobile devices, mapping and geo-tagging should be included in the new curricula.

DISCUSSION

All in all, the outcomes of the Mongolian journalism training have already created its space and offer all levels of academic courses from undergraduate to postgraduate levels to prepare the human resources for Mongolian media locally. Journalism training has enough highly qualified professors and its own curricula as well. However, there are a number of issues facing Mongolian universities that are offering journalism courses such as renewing the standards and curricula, organizing practice-dominated training, enriching technical and personnel resources, providing professional development programs for professors, improving the quality of the training, improving the quality of the textbooks and materials that have been used and improve the new students' basic knowledge. All universities and institutions agree on these issues. It is necessary to increase the number of students because the universities are funded by the students' tuition fees. In this case, there are limited opportunities for improving the learning environment and professional development of the professors. As a result, there is low-priced and low-quality education in the society and in turn, this increases the demand for qualified journalists. Maulet (2013), who is a professor in the NUM journalism department, presents his point on this issue, "Although having many universities brings advantages to the competition and improvement of pluralism in the society, it is too much for Mongolia to have 18 universities preparing journalists. In our case, 5 universities would be enough to prepare local journalists". Therefore, the Mongolian government should consider this issue seriously in order to raise the journalism training to the world standards through the appropriate policy on the organization of Mongolian journalism education in the higher education system.

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